

Three-dimensional characterization of an oxide scale on ATI 718Plus[®] superalloy

Adam Kruk^a, Sebastian Lech^{a,*}, Aleksander Gil^b, Grzegorz Cempura^a, Alina Agüero^c,
Agnieszka M. Wusatowska-Sarnek^d, Aleksandra Czyrska-Filemonowicz^a

^a AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH-UST), International Centre of Electron Microscopy for Materials Science and Faculty of Metals Engineering and Industrial Computer Science, al. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059, Krakow, Poland

^b AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH-UST), Faculty of Materials Science and Ceramics, al. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059, Krakow, Poland

^c Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA), Departamento de Materiales y Estructuras, Torrejón de Ardoz, Spain

^d Pratt & Whitney, 400 Main Street, East Hartford, CT, 06108, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

- A. Superalloys
- B. SEM
- B. TEM
- B. STEM
- C. High temperature corrosion
- C. Internal oxidation

ABSTRACT

The presented study was devoted to the characterization of a scale formed on the ATI 718Plus[®] superalloy. Novel complementary techniques were applied to precisely describe the structure, chemistry, morphology of the scale as well as the spatial distribution of phases formed during oxidation. The study revealed a discontinuous interlayer of the δ -Ni₃Nb phase that had developed underneath the protective Cr₂O₃ scale. Al₂O₃ particles, which had precipitated predominantly at grain boundaries, and isolated chromia particles were present in the internal oxidation zone. Nanosized γ phase precipitates enriched with Fe and Co were embedded into the scale.

1. Introduction

The ATI 718Plus[®] (henceforth referred to as 718Plus) is a polycrystalline nickel-based superalloy designed to replace the widely used Inconel 718 (IN718) superalloy in certain applications [1]. Owing to an excellent combination of mechanical and oxidation behaviour at high temperature, both superalloys are considered suitable for the construction of critical rotating components (compressor and turbine disks) in aircraft and power generation parts. The 718Plus exhibits improved chemical composition compared to conventional IN718, which stems from its optimized microstructure; this has allowed the upper operating temperature threshold to be increased from 650 to about 700 °C [2,3]. The microstructure of 718Plus consists of a γ matrix strengthened with spherical γ' -Ni₃(Al, Ti, Nb) precipitates within grains and plate-like precipitates of the η -Ni₆AlNb phase at grain boundaries [4–6]. Since the γ'' phase was unstable at high temperature, it was eliminated in favour of the γ' phase, while in the IN718 superalloy both phases are present [7].

The oxidation resistance of the 718Plus superalloy had previously been investigated at temperatures in the range of 650–1000 °C, with both short [3,8–10] and long-time [11–13] exposures considered.

Huenert et al. [8] and Unocic et al. [12] compared the oxidation behaviour of the 718Plus and IN718 superalloys, concluding that the oxidation resistance of 718Plus is superior to that of IN718. When oxidized, the 718Plus superalloy develops a protective Cr₂O₃ scale. Beneath it, an internal oxidation zone forms; in this zone, alumina precipitates are present and Cr-depletion of the matrix is observed [8,9,11]. Moreover, the formation of a Nb-rich interlayer beneath the chromia scale had been reported [8,11]; it was identified in our previous study [3] as the δ -Ni₃Nb phase. Furthermore, Asala et al. [10] investigated the hot corrosion behaviour of additively manufactured 718Plus and found a thin layer of Nb-rich oxide sandwiched between two parts of the chromia scale. Although the afore-mentioned studies reported significant findings, a detailed characterization of phases formed during the oxidation of 718Plus is still required, especially with regard to their morphology and distribution in 3D space as well as mutual interaction.

The present study is devoted to a multiscale 2D and 3D characterization of the scale and near-surface region formed in the 718Plus superalloy during up to 4000 h of oxidation in synthetic air at 850 °C. Advanced electron microscopic and spectroscopic techniques were combined with tomography based on a combination of the focused ion

* Corresponding author at: AGH University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Metals Engineering and Industrial Computer Science, International Centre of Electron Microscopy for Materials Science, al. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059, Krakow, Poland.

E-mail addresses: kruczek@agh.edu.pl (A. Kruk), slech@agh.edu.pl (S. Lech), gil@agh.edu.pl (A. Gil), cempura@agh.edu.pl (G. Cempura), agueroba@inta.es (A. Agüero), agnieszka.wusatowska-sarnek@prattwhitney.com (A.M. Wusatowska-Sarnek), czyrska@agh.edu.pl (A. Czyrska-Filemonowicz).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2020.108634>

Received 18 December 2019; Received in revised form 20 March 2020; Accepted 23 March 2020

Available online 04 April 2020

0010-938X/ © 2020 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

beam and scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

The material used for the study was the ATI 718Plus® polycrystalline nickel-based superalloy with a nominal chemical composition of Ni-18Cr-9.7Fe-9.2Co-5.5Nb-2.7Mo-1W-1.5Al-0.75Ti-0.02C (wt%). It had been produced via vacuum induction melting and vacuum arc remelting followed by rotary forging and ring rolling. A 100 mm bar was cut from a ring and underwent a standard heat treatment that involved solution treatment (968 °C, 1 h, oil quenching) followed by two-step ageing at 788 °C (8 h) and 704 °C (8 h), and then cooling in air [14]. The microstructure of 718Plus after such heat treatment was composed of a γ (Ni-based solid solution) matrix with spherical γ' -Ni₃(Al, Ti, Nb) precipitates inside the γ grains and a plate-like η -Ni₆AlNb phase formed mainly at grain boundaries. Aside from these phases, some M(C,N) primary carbonitrides, orthorhombic δ -Ni₃Nb and hexagonal η -Ni₃Ti or Ni₆(Al,Ti)Nb particles, and topologically close-packed (TCP) phases had also been observed in the 718Plus superalloy [4,5,15]. The microstructure as well as phase and chemical composition of the as-received superalloy were described in detail in Refs [9,16,17].

Prior to oxidation, the prepared coupons (20 × 10 × 5 mm) were ground on all sides using SiC abrasive papers with increasing grit (up to 180 grit) and cleaned in acetone. The samples were then weighed and oxidized in a horizontal tube furnace; the description of the closed-loop laboratory rig used at INTA is given elsewhere [18]. Oxidation tests were performed in synthetic air (20 vol.% pure oxygen with 80 vol.% pure nitrogen) at 850 °C for 120, 1000, 2000 and 4000 h. Afterwards, selected samples were prepared for further investigation by means of various techniques described in the subsequent section.

2.2. Sample preparation and characterization by electron microscopy

Scanning, transmission and scanning-transmission electron microscopy (SEM, TEM and STEM, respectively) were used to examine the oxide scale and the near-surface region formed in the 718Plus alloy after oxidation. These techniques were complemented with electron diffraction and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS).

The oxidized samples were protected with an adhesive Teflon tape to prevent damage to the oxide scales. The samples were cut using a low-speed diamond saw (IsoMet 5000, Buehler). A thin, protective nickel layer was then deposited electrochemically at a temperature of 50 °C and a voltage of 3 V using the following solution: 260 g of NiSO₄·7H₂O, 30 g of NiCl₂·6H₂O, 30 g of H₃BO₃, 1000 mL of H₂O. Finally, the sectioned samples were hot-mounted in a conductive resin (PolyFast, Struers), ground and polished using a colloidal silica suspension for at least 30 min.

The SEM analyses were conducted using a high-resolution Merlin Gemini II microscope (ZEISS) equipped with a Schottky field-emission gun and an EDX detector with a Quantax 800 microanalysis system (Bruker). The SEM images were obtained using secondary electrons (SE) and backscattered electrons (BSE) with an angle-selective backscatter (AsB) detector.

For TEM/STEM investigations, ultra-thin specimens (lamellae) were prepared directly from selected areas of the oxidized samples via the FIB technique, using the NEON CrossBeam 40EsB (ZEISS). The lamellae were prepared by sputtering their surfaces with Ga⁺ ions emitted from a source with liquid metal. Prior to sputtering, a thin Pt layer was deposited on the area of interest (AOI) on the specimen's surface, with the intention of protecting the scale's surface from being damaged. The lamellae (approx. size of 10 × 10 μm) were cut perpendicularly to the surface of the investigated specimen. The final thinning, down to a level of several dozen nanometres, was performed after mounting the sample in a copper grid. This method minimizes the occurrence of artefacts

during sample preparation and can be used to obtain thin and clean lamellae of uniform thickness, suitable for high-resolution imaging and quantitative analyses.

The TEM/STEM analyses were performed using a Tecnai G2 20 Twin microscope (FEI) and a probe corrected Titan Cubed G2 60–300 microscope (FEI) equipped with the ChemiSTEM™ system [19]. High-resolution STEM images were acquired using a high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector. Phase identification was conducted by means of selected area electron diffraction (SAED) in conjunction with EDXS results and the JEMS software [20]. The EDXS data was acquired either at an accelerating voltage of 200 or 300 kV – in the case of TEM and STEM analyses, or 5 or 15 kV – for SEM analyses. The SEM-EDX data analyses were performed with standardless PhiRhoZ (for 5 kV) and peak-to-background ZAF (for 15 kV) quantification methods, while STEM-EDX data was analyzed using the Esprit software (Bruker) in which the standardless Cliff-Lorimer quantification method had been selected.

2.3. Characterization via FIB-SEM tomography

In order to collect the data for tomographic reconstruction, the slice-and-view technique was applied; this method is based on an alternating process of sectioning and imaging (serial sectioning) [21]. For SEM imaging, both SE and BSE detectors were used, while high-energy FIB milling was performed using a Ga⁺ ion beam. Fig. 1 illustrates the process of data acquisition for further FIB-SEM tomographic reconstruction. As in the case of the preparation of lamellae using FIB, an AOI is selected first based on SEM observations of the surface of the oxidized sample (Fig. 1a). The AOI is then coated with platinum (Fig. 1b) to minimize negative effects during serial sectioning. Later, the material surrounding the AOI is removed using high-current FIB milling, revealing the sample cross-section for further serial sectioning (Fig. 1c). Finally, FIB sectioning and SEM-SE/BSE imaging are used to collect a series of images, as indicated in Fig. 1d. The serial FIB milling was carried out by employing a NEON CrossBeam 40EsB (ZEISS) using a Ga⁺ ion beam at a voltage of 30 kV (beam current of 1 nA) and approx. 50 nm steps. The SEM-BSE images were acquired at an accelerating voltage of 2 kV using a 60 μm aperture. The applied parameters resulted in a voxel size of 25 × 25 × 50 nm and the acquisition of 325 grayscale images with a resolution of 1024 × 768 pixels for each detector. Altogether, raw data was obtained for a total sample volume of almost 8000 μm³. Lastly, datasets were processed, reconstructed and visualized in 3D using the Fiji and Avizo 6.3 applications. Basic processing included stack alignment, image processing and segmentation based on the Z-contrast.

3. Results and discussion

The microstructure as well as phase and chemical composition of the 718Plus superalloy oxidized in synthetic air at 850 °C for up to 4000 h differed significantly from those observed for the as-received material. The results of our previous investigations of the as-received 718Plus superalloy as well as its samples exposed to oxidation tests with a shorter duration (120 h) had already been published in Refs [3,9]. The present paper discusses the changes in the oxide scale and near-surface region formed on this superalloy after significantly longer oxidation tests (1000 and 4000 h).

Table 1 presents the mass gains of the 718Plus superalloy samples in relation to their unit surface area, after 120, 1000 and 4000 h of oxidation. The observed mass gain of about 1 mg per 1 cm² after 4000 h of oxidation at 850 °C is typical for nickel-based superalloys that form protective Cr₂O₃ scales [22–24].

Fig. 2 shows the microstructure of the samples oxidized for 120, 1000 and 4000 h, cross-sectioned via FIB, and imaged by means of SEM-BSE. Due to a significant difference in the thickness of the oxide scales formed on the investigated samples, their microstructures are presented

Fig. 1. (A) SEM-SE image of an oxide scale formed on the 718Plus superalloy after 120 h of oxidation in air at 850 °C (tilted sample); (B) selected area coated with platinum (SEM-SE); (C) SEM-SE image of the sample before serial sectioning (slice-and-view technique); (D) Scheme of the sample cube geometry optimized for FIB serial sectioning procedure.

Table 1

Mass gain per surface area in the 718Plus superalloy oxidized at 850 °C up to 4000 h in synthetic air.

Time [h]	120	1000	4000
Mass gain [mg/cm ²]	0.4	0.8	1.1

using images obtained under different magnification (Fig. 2A, B, C). Nevertheless, to facilitate comparison, the areas marked with white rectangles are shown under the same magnification in Fig. 2D, E, F. This makes it possible to illustrate how the thickness and the microstructure of the interlayer formed directly underneath the Cr₂O₃ scale (found to consist of the δ-Ni₃Nb phase, as shown further) changed over time. At sites where this layer was not continuous, Cr₂O₃ intrusions were observed (marked with black arrows in Fig. 2E). Individual precipitates of the δ phase with an elongated shape were found in the chromium-depletion zone of the γ matrix (Fig. 2A, B, C). Even though the mechanism underlying the δ phase formation was not the subject of our research, some possibilities were considered. The δ-Ni₃Nb phase may presumably form as a result of η-Ni₆AlNb decomposition, which is in turn a consequence of the oxidation reaction of aluminium present in η phase. It is well-established that Al₂O₃ is much more thermodynamically stable than Cr₂O₃, and its formation is preferred when the concentration of chromium is not significantly higher than that of aluminium [25]. The activity of oxygen under the Cr₂O₃ scale formed on the 718Plus superalloy is sufficient for the oxidation of the aluminium present in η phase, in accordance with the reaction:

The metallic nickel formed as a result dissolves in the γ matrix, while aluminium oxidized to Al₂O₃ forms an internal oxidation zone underneath the Cr₂O₃ scale. Since the concentration of chromium in the γ matrix of the internal oxidation zone is always lower than in-depth/at a greater depth, it cannot be excluded that – given the condition that the concentration of chromium in the γ matrix is reduced – the η-Ni₆AlNb phase undergoes dissolution. Afterwards, the dissolved elements form the δ phase beneath the chromia scale, where chromium

concentration is the lowest, but also at other sites in the chromium-depletion zone. Lastly, the nickel and aluminium released in this process are dissolved in the γ matrix.

The η phase is not the only aluminium reservoir for the internal oxidation process; the γ'-Ni₃(Al,Ti,Nb) phase is another one. As shown in our previous study [9], the γ' phase is unstable in the chromium-depletion zone, where after 120 h of oxidation the depth of the γ'-free zone ranged between 8 and 10 μm.

Fig. 3 shows the internal oxidation zone composed of Al₂O₃ and developed for different oxidation times – its depth is marked with white dashed lines and the vertical arrows. This zone reached a depth of about 6, 10 and 20 μm after 120, 1000 and 4000 h of oxidation, respectively. For each of these samples, an SEM-EDXS line scan analysis was performed for selected chemical elements.

Fig. 4 shows the concentration vs. distance from the sample surface profiles of O, Al, Cr, Ni, Nb and Ti, acquired along the dotted line marked in the SEM image of the sample oxidized for 4000 h. As can be seen, the highest concentrations of chromium and oxygen were found in the ~10 μm thick area corresponding to the location of the chromia scale. Moreover, a higher concentration of titanium was observed in the outermost part of the oxide scale, indicating the formation of Ti-rich oxides. Directly beneath the chromia scale, the highest concentration of nickel and niobium can be seen, correlating with the presence of δ-Ni₃Nb phase, which was about 2 μm thick in the sample oxidized for 4000 h (Fig. 2F). Two areas with comparable concentrations of these elements were found in the chromium-depletion zone, where the profile line passes through δ/η precipitates. Based solely on this analysis, it is not possible to determine whether these precipitates consisted of δ or η. Although the concentration of niobium in these precipitates seems to be different, it should be emphasized that this may related to the 200 nm resolution of the performed EDXS line scan analysis, and not to the difference in chemical composition. A similar anomaly may be observed in the two aluminium oxides found along this line profile, in the case of which the signal from the thinner oxide is combined with that from the γ matrix. Finally, the chromium concentration profile confirms that the Cr-depletion zone reached a depth of approx. 20 μm, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 5 shows the TEM bright-field (BF) image of the microstructure of 718Plus oxidized for 1000 h (Fig. 5A), the STEM-EDXS element distribution maps (Fig. 5B-F) of selected chemical elements (Cr, O, Ni,

Fig. 2. (A–C) Cross-sectional SEM-BSE images of the near-surface microstructure of the 718Plus superalloy after 120, 1000 and 4000 h of oxidation at 850 °C; (D–F) Magnified images of areas marked with white rectangles in Fig. 2A–C.

Nb and Al), and the electron diffraction (SAED) patterns (Fig. 5G–I) obtained for areas 1, 2 and 3 in Fig. 5A. The distributions of Ni and Nb as well as Cr and O indicate that between the Cr_2O_3 scale and the γ substrate there is a region strongly enriched in the δ - Ni_3Nb phase, as revealed by the SAED pattern for area 1 (Fig. 5G). As mentioned, the δ phase precipitates, although very numerous, do not form a continuous layer underneath the Cr_2O_3 scale. There were several sites where chromia, forming intrusions, remained in contact either with the alumina or γ matrix, as indicated by the SAED pattern for area 2 (Fig. 5H). As revealed by the STEM-EDXS element distribution maps of Al and O (Fig. 4B, F), alumina precipitates were also found in the analyzed area.

Based on the SAED pattern for area 3, this phase was identified as γ - Al_2O_3 (Fig. 5I). The presence of the γ - Al_2O_3 phase in the internal oxidation zone had been reported by Schumann and Rühle [26], who oxidized a single crystal of γ '- Ni_3Al at 950 °C.

Fig. 6A shows an STEM-BF image obtained for the area of the Cr_2O_3 scale close to its boundary with the substrate. Fig. 6B shows a magnified fragment of this area, highlighting some particles present within it and a SAED pattern for the area marked with a dashed circle. It should be noted that fine particles (diameter of less than 10 nm) remained spherical, while larger ones are faceted. Fig. 6C shows a high-resolution STEM-HAADF image of γ particles embedded in the chromia scale.

Fig. 3. Cross-sectional SEM-SE images of the Al_2O_3 internal oxidation zone formed in the 718Plus superalloy after 120, 1000 and 4000 h of oxidation at 850 °C.

Fig. 4. EDXS concentration vs. depth profiles of O, Al, Cr, Ni, Nb and Ti, acquired along the dashed white line marked in the cross-sectional image (SEM-SE) of the 718Plus superalloy after 4000 h of oxidation at 850 °C.

Fig. 6D shows a filtered image of one of the fine particle (pointed out with an arrow in Fig. 6C); the red circle corresponds to the diameter of this particle. It should be emphasized that a considerable distortion of the arrangement of atomic columns is observed for this particle, as highlighted in Fig. 6E. On the other hand, Fig. 6F shows a filtered HRSTEM-HAADF image of the nanostructure of Cr_2O_3 at the atomic level, as seen along the $[422\bar{3}]$ zone axis, with a superimposed simulated

image of the same Cr_2O_3 arrangement.

Fig. 7 presents the STEM-EDXS distribution maps of selected elements (O, Cr, Ni, Fe and Co) acquired for the area marked with the white rectangle in Fig. 6A. They revealed that the main elements comprising the particles were Ni, Fe and Co. Based on the aforementioned maps, the HRSTEM-HAADF images, and the electron diffraction (SAED) patterns obtained for selected particles, they were identified as the γ phase.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, such particles have never been reported in the literature on the oxidation of the IN718 and 718Plus superalloys. However, iron-rich precipitates within the internally growing Cr_2O_3 scale had already been observed in the case of the Crofer 22 APU ferritic steel [27]. They were present in areas where – in the earlier stages of oxidation – protrusions from the metallic substrate into the oxide scale had formed. The rate of scale growth over such metallic protrusions gradually decreased due to the extended path of diffusion of chromium from the bulk material to the oxide-alloy boundary. These protrusions were eventually absorbed into the scale, forming chromium-free spherical forms. In the case of the 718Plus superalloy, it is rather unlikely (however not impossible) that the formation of metallic particles inside the chromia scale occurs via a similar mechanism. It should be emphasized that γ phase particles found within the chromia scale formed on the 718Plus are significantly smaller than the iron-rich precipitates formed in the case of the Crofer 22 APU steel. In the present study, the largest particles found in the 718Plus did not exceed 200 nm in diameter, while fine particles (diameter of less than 10 nm) were significantly more numerous. In the case of the superalloy, intermediate forms, namely intrusions of different size, were not found at the oxide/alloy boundary; on the other hand, they were observed for the Crofer 22 APU steel. It should be emphasized that γ phase particles were not found in the 718Plus samples oxidized for 120 h, whereas they were present in the chromia scale formed after 1000 and 4000 h of oxidation. Moreover, it should be noted that the zone containing such precipitates increased with oxidation time. It appears that these particles had precipitated from the chromia instead of getting trapped inside it during scale growth. This seems to be supported by the existence of small, spherical precipitates (Fig. 6B-D) and the faceted shape of the larger ones. Further investigation of this issue is in progress.

Of the three investigated 718Plus samples, only two (oxidized for 120 and 1000 h) were viable for 3D tomographic reconstruction using the FIB-SEM technique. In the case of the sample oxidized for 4000 h, the scale and the internal oxidation zone were too thick to allow analysis. The results of 3D imaging and the properties of the scale formed after 120 h of oxidation had already been reported in Ref. [7]. In the present paper, the results of tomographic reconstruction of structural elements developed in the sample oxidized for 1000 h are reported. It should be noted that the examination was not limited to the scale and near-surface region – the analyzed areas also featured a significant part of the bulk material containing lamellar precipitates of the η phase.

Fig. 8 shows the SEM-BSE image along with SEM-EDXS element distribution maps acquired after the serial sectioning procedure for 3D tomographic reconstruction using the slice-and-view technique (the area for which this analysis was performed is marked with a black

Fig. 5. (A) TEM-BF image of oxide scale formed on the 718Plus superalloy (850 °C, 1000 h); (B–F) STEM-EDXS distribution maps of selected elements; (G–I) Electron diffraction patterns for areas 1-3 in Fig. 5A.

arrow in Fig. 1C). This image represents the last slice which had a microstructure that was consistent with the microstructure of a certain number of slices before it; this made it possible to correlate the EDXS element distribution maps with the tomographic results. Moreover, the lamella prepared from the sample oxidized for 1000 h was prepared directly from the area adjacent to the last slice collected for tomographic reconstruction. This approach allows the results of FIB-SEM tomography to be correlated with TEM/STEM observations in a more straightforward manner. The analysis of the O, Ni and Nb distribution maps indicates the formation of a non-oxide phase (possibly the δ or η phase) beneath the Cr_2O_3 scale. This observation is consistent with the results of our previous study [3], which showed that a discontinuous interlayer of the δ phase forms beneath the Cr_2O_3 scale in the 718Plus

oxidized for 120 h. Furthermore, from the titanium distribution map it can be concluded that this element was to some degree oxidized internally, which led to the formation of oxides within the internal oxidation zone. On the other hand, some of it was oxidized externally, forming oxides on the surface of the Cr_2O_3 scale.

Fig. 9A shows a 3D image created using tomographic reconstruction, which illustrates the spatial distribution of two oxide phases (Cr_2O_3 and Al_2O_3), two intermetallic phases (δ/η) and porosity. It should be noted that the x, y, z axes correspond to the geometry of the sample prepared for FIB serial sectioning shown in Fig. 1D. Fig. 9B-E present the reconstructed 3D visualizations representing the volume of each phase separately in a front view, parallel to the slicing direction along the z-axis (Fig. 1D). As can be seen in Fig. 9B, the Cr_2O_3 scale has

Fig. 6. (A) STEM-HAADF image of the bottom part of the chromia scale formed on the 718Plus superalloy oxidized at 850 °C for 4000 h; (B) selected area highlighting the presence of γ particles in the chromia scale (STEM-HAADF) with the corresponding electron diffraction pattern for the area marked with the white dashed circle; (C) High-resolution STEM-HAADF image of fine γ particles within the chromia scale; (D) Filtered high-resolution STEM-HAADF image of the particle pointed out in Fig. 6C; (E) Filtered high-resolution STEM-HAADF image of the area marked with the red circle in Fig. 6D, showing the distortions in the Cr_2O_3 crystal lattice, caused by the presence of γ phase; (F) Filtered high-resolution STEM-HAADF image showing the arrangement of chromium atom columns in the chromia scale with a corresponding simulated HAADF image of Cr_2O_3 [4223] plane (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

a strongly developed boundary with the phase located beneath it (δ/η). The scale is also characterized by a large number of pores (Fig. 9E). Single Cr_2O_3 precipitates were found within the internal oxidation zone consisting of Al_2O_3 precipitates, even at depths that in some cases reached this zone's boundary. This indicates that Al_2O_3 interfaces seem to be favourable sites for the nucleation of Cr_2O_3 . The bulk material also featured pores, some of which were significantly larger than those found in the scale. Based on a single measurement it is impossible to determine with absolute certainty whether the two enormous pores near the bottom right corner in the 3D visualisation (Fig. 9E) were not accidental, three-dimensional structural defects. It should be emphasized that this type of porosity may be attributed to a number of processes that occur underneath the Cr_2O_3 scale. The growth of the Cr_2O_3 scale is accompanied by the diffusion of chromium atoms from the γ matrix to the oxide scale. The higher the flux of chromium atoms, the greater the concentration of vacancies generated in the γ matrix, which can undergo coalescence and form pores. Beneath the Cr_2O_3 scale, in the chromium-depletion zone, precipitates of alumina, chromia and intermetallic δ phase are present, but at the same time the precipitates of the intermetallic η - Ni_6AlNb and γ' - $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Al}, \text{Ti}, \text{Nb})$ phases are no longer found. Some of the afore-mentioned processes may generate compressive stress, while others may generate tensile ones. It therefore cannot be excluded that the porosity observed beneath the oxide scale is a consequence of compensation between these stresses.

Subsequently, a correlation between the 718Plus microstructure and the spatial distribution of Al_2O_3 precipitates in the internal oxidation zone was taken into consideration. To visualise this, the reconstructed

Al_2O_3 phase is shown in Fig. 10A in a top view, i.e. one perpendicular to the y-axis of the ion beam. This 3D reconstruction shows regions with a significantly higher density of Al_2O_3 precipitates, as well as empty spaces between them. This visualization was not sufficient to determine with certainty whether the afore-mentioned correlation exists. The number of slices in the y-axis was therefore limited by inserting an orthoslice at a depth of about 7 μm below the top of the reconstructed volume. This made the correlation between the distribution of the Al_2O_3 precipitates and grain boundaries clearly visible. Fig. 10C shows the virtual image of the microstructure of the 718Plus that was used as a reference point in Fig. 10B. It is evident that alumina was located mainly at the grain boundaries of the γ phase.

Fig. 11 presents a tomographic reconstruction of the distribution of the intermetallic phases (δ/η), which, as mentioned, could not be distinguished based on the Z-contrast. The main aspect seen based on the top view is the discontinuous nature of the δ layer formed beneath the chromia scale (Fig. 11A). The other view – from a different perspective (Fig. 11B) – shows that both δ and η phases were present in the γ matrix beneath the δ layer. Based on previous observations, it can be assumed that plate-like precipitates of η phase are thinner than the δ ones [16,28] and are located deeper beneath the oxide scale.

The δ - Ni_3Nb phase does not contain chromium, which is why it most likely does not provide a diffusion path for this element, unlike the γ -phase solid solution. Thus, after the formation of the δ phase layer, the reaction between chromium and oxygen atoms can occur predominantly at those sites where chromium oxide had remained in contact with alumina and/or the γ phase. The only sites where the

Fig. 7. STEM-HAADF image of the area marked with a white rectangle in Fig. 6A (A) with corresponding STEM-EDXS distribution maps of selected elements (B–F).

Cr_2O_3 scale had remained in contact with the afore-mentioned phases are the γ -phase “channels” found inside the δ phase layer and beneath it – in the internal oxidation zone of aluminium. It should be emphasized that the amount of chromium that can be stored in these channels is limited due to their small size. The diffusion paths of chromium from bulk material are therefore severely limited due to the presence of alumina as well as the δ and η phases, and, occasionally, pores in the chromium-depletion zone (Fig. 12A). Fig. 12B shows a 3D reconstruction from the same perspective applied in Fig. 12A, but limited only to Cr_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 phases. This reconstruction shows that chromium oxide present within the internal oxidation zone of aluminium

remained in contact with the previously formed Al_2O_3 precipitates in the vast majority of precipitates. Sometimes these oxides remained in contact with the scale, forming deep intrusions; however, a significant number had formed separate precipitates (Fig. 12B). It can be presumed that the local concentration of chromium in the γ matrix had been so low that the oxidation in this area was interrupted. Thus, the oxygen dissolved in the solid solution of the γ phase had to diffuse to deeper parts of the bulk material, where the chromium concentration was higher. It is via this mechanism that separate Cr_2O_3 particles had formed despite having no contact with the scale. In most cases, they formed at the interface between the Al_2O_3 particles and the γ matrix.

Fig. 8. (A) Cross-sectional SEM-BSE image of the near-surface microstructure of the 718Plus superalloy oxidized at 850 °C for 1000 h, based on the last slice during the serial sectioning procedure. (B–H) Corresponding SEM-EDXS distribution maps of selected elements, acquired after the serial sectioning procedure.

Fig. 9. (A) 3D visualization of the microstructure of the oxide scale formed on the 718Plus superalloy after 1000 h of oxidation in dry air at 850 °C, rendered via tomographic reconstruction; (B–E) Microstructural features of individual components: B) Cr_2O_3 , C) Al_2O_3 , D) δ and η phases, E) pores.

Fig. 10. 3D tomographic reconstruction of the distribution of the Al_2O_3 phase: A) top view; B) top view with an orthoslice inserted at the depth of $7\ \mu\text{m}$ from the top; C) the orthoslice used to generate image 10B.

This can be supported by the fact that the interface of the Al_2O_3 phase seems to be a nucleation site for the Cr_2O_3 phase.

4. Conclusions

The paper shows an original approach to the characterization of oxide scales grown on the 718Plus superalloy by means of FIB-SEM tomography combined with advanced electron microscopic and spectroscopic techniques. The large volume of tomographic data provides detailed information about the morphology and distribution of phases in three-dimensional space. The major findings of this study are as follows:

- A discontinuous δ - Ni_3Nb interlayer was found underneath the Cr_2O_3 scale.
- Al_2O_3 precipitates in the internal oxidation zone formed mainly at grain boundaries in the metallic substrate.
- Isolated Cr_2O_3 precipitates were found in the internal oxidation zone.

Fig. 11. 3D tomographic reconstruction of the δ and η phases: A) top view; B) perspective view.

- Numerous precipitates of the γ phase enriched in Fe and Co were found in the interior of the Cr_2O_3 scale, near the interface with the metallic substrate. Their size ranged from 5 to 10 to several tens of nanometers. Small particles had a spherical shape, whereas the larger ones were faceted.
- The findings based on microscopic examination combined with 3D imaging allowed a detailed description of the structure, chemistry, morphology and spatial distribution of phases formed in the oxidized 718Plus superalloy to be presented.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adam Kruk: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Resources, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Sebastian Lech:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Aleksander Gil:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Grzegorz Cempura:** Investigation. **Alina Agüero:** Resources. **Agnieszka M. Wusatowska-Sarnek:** Resources, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Aleksandra Czyska-Filemonowicz:** Conceptualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 12. (A) 3D tomographic reconstruction of the microstructural features of the near-surface area (front view); (B) the same image as 12A, but limited to Cr_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 , with an orthoslice inserted at a distance of $3\ \mu\text{m}$ along the z-axis.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge Pratt & Whitney, CT, USA for providing the material used in this study and the financial support to some part of the research. Part of the study has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under agreement No. 823717 ESTEEM3. We also acknowledge KMM-VIN for supporting the collaboration between AGH-UST and INTA.

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

References

- [1] R.L. Kennedy, Allvac® 718Plus™, superalloy for the next forty years, *Superalloys 718* (625) (2005) 1–14, https://doi.org/10.7449/2005/Superalloys_2005_1_14 706 Var. Deriv. 2005.
- [2] W.-D. Cao, R. Kennedy, Role of chemistry in 718-type Alloys - Allvac® 718Plus™ alloy development, *Superalloys 2004* (2004) 91–99.
- [3] S. Lech, A. Kruk, A. Gil, G. Cempura, A. Agüero, A. Czyska-Filemonowicz, Three-dimensional imaging and characterization of the oxide scale formed on a polycrystalline nickel-based superalloy, *Scr. Mater.* 167 (2019) 16–20, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2019.03.027>.
- [4] E.J. Pickering, H. Mathur, a. Bhowmik, O.M.D.M. Messé, J.S. Barnard, M.C. Hardy, R. Krakow, K. Loehnert, H.J. Stone, C.M.F. Rae, Grain-boundary precipitation in Allvac 718Plus, *Acta Mater.* 60 (2012) 2757–2769, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2012.01.042>.

- [5] O.M. Messé, J.S. Barnard, E.J. Pickering, P.A. Midgley, C.M.F. Rae, On the precipitation of delta phase in ALLVAC® 718Plus, *Philos. Mag. Abingdon (Abingdon)* 94 (2014) 1132–1152, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786435.2013.878052>.
- [6] A. Kruk, G. Cempura, S. Lech, A. Czyska-Filemonowicz, STEM-EDX and FIB-SEM tomography of Allvac 718Plus superalloy, *Arch. Metall. Mater.* 61 (2016) 535–541, <https://doi.org/10.1515/amm-2016-0093>.
- [7] R. Cozar, A. Pineau, Morphology of γ' and γ'' precipitates and thermal stability of inconel 718 type alloys, *Metall. Trans.* 4 (1973) 47–59, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02649604>.
- [8] D. Huenert, M. Proebstle, A. Casanova, R. Schluetter, R. Krakow, M. Buescher, P. Randelzhofer, A. Evans, K. Loehnert, T. Witulski, S. Neumeier, C.M.F. Rae, ATI718PLUS® – new nickel based disc alloy and its capability, *Superalloys 2016 13th Int. Symp* (2016).
- [9] S. Lech, A. Gil, G. Cempura, A. Agüero, A. Kruk, A. Czyska-Filemonowicz, Microstructure of an oxide scale formed on ATI 718Plus superalloy during oxidation at 850 °C characterised using analytical electron microscopy, *Int. J. Mater. Res.* 110 (2019) 42–48, <https://doi.org/10.3139/146.111675>.
- [10] G. Asala, J. Andersson, O.A. Ojo, Hot corrosion behaviour of wire-arc additive manufactured Ni-based superalloy ATI 718Plus®, *Corros. Sci.* 158 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2019.07.010>.
- [11] K.A. Unocic, R.R. Unocic, B.A. Pint, R.W. Hayes, Effect of microstructure and environment on the High-temperature oxidation behavior of alloy 718Plus, 7th Int. Symp. Superalloy 718 Deriv (2010) 977–991, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118495223.ch74>.
- [12] K.A. Unocic, B.A. Pint, Effect of environment on the High temperature oxidation behavior of 718 and 718Plus, 8th Int. Symp. Superalloy 718 Deriv (2014) 667–677.
- [13] B.A. Pint, S. Dryepondt, K.A. Unocic, OXIDATION OF SUPERALLOYS IN EXTREME ENVIRONMENTS, 7th Int. Symp. Superalloy 718 Deriv (2010) 861–875 2010.
- [14] E. Mcdevitt, Nickel-base Alloy Heat Treatments, Nickel-base Alloys, and Articles Including Nickel-base Alloys, WO 2013/081770, (2013) <https://www.google.com/patents/WO2013081770A1>.
- [15] R. Krakow, D.N. Johnstone, A.S. Eggeman, D. Hüner, M.C. Hardy, C.M.F. Rae, P.A. Midgley, On the crystallography and composition of topologically close-packed phases in ATI 718Plus®, *Acta Mater.* 130 (2017) 271–280, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2017.03.038>.
- [16] A. Kruk, G. Cempura, S. Lech, A.M. Wusatowska-Sarnek, A. Czyska-Filemonowicz, Application of analytical electron microscopy and tomographic techniques for metrology and 3D imaging of microstructural elements in Allvac® 718Plus™, Proc.9th Int. Symp. Superalloy 718 Deriv. Energy, Aerospace, Ind. Appl (2018) 1035–1050, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-89480-5_69.
- [17] S. Lech, A. Kruk, G. Cempura, A. Gruszczynski, A. Gil, A. Agüero, A.M. Wusatowska-Sarnek, A. Czyska-Filemonowicz, Influence of high-temperature exposure on the microstructure of ATI 718Plus superalloy studied by Electron microscopy and tomography techniques, *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.* (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-019-04474-5>.
- [18] A. Agüero, V. González, M. Gutiérrez, R. Muelas, Oxidation under pure steam: Cr based protective oxides and coatings, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 237 (2013) 30–38, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2013.09.016>.
- [19] FEI, P. Schlossmacher, D.O. Klenov, B. Freitag, S. Von Harrach, A. Steinbach, Nanoscale chemical compositional analysis with an innovative S/TEM-EDX system, *microsc. Anal. Nanotechnol. Suppl* 24 (2010) S5–S8 <http://www.microscopy-analysis.com/magazine/issues/nanoscale-chemical-compositional-analysis-innovative-stem-edx-system>.
- [20] P. Stadelmann, JEMS, Java Electron Microscopy Software, (2020) (n.d.). <https://www.jems-swiss.ch/> (Accessed November 11, 2019).
- [21] L. Holzer, M. Cantoni, Review of FIB-tomography, in: I. Utke, S. Moshkalev (Eds.), *Nanofabrication Using Focus. Ion Electron Beams Princ. Appl*, Oxford University Press, 2012, pp. 410–435.
- [22] J. Zurek, D.J. Young, E. Essuman, H.J. Penkalla, L. Niewolak, W.J. Quadackers, Growth and adherence of chromia based surface scales on Ni-base alloys in high- and low-pO₂ gases, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A.* 477 (2008) 259–270, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2007.05.035>.
- [23] T. Dudziak, K. Jura, A. Polkowska, V. Deodeshmukh, M. Warmuzek, M. Witkowska, W. Ratuszek, K. Chrusciel, Steam Oxidation Resistance of Advanced Steels and Ni-Based Alloys at 700 °C for 1000 h, *Oxid. Met.* 89 (2018) 755–779, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11085-017-9818-1>.
- [24] T. Dudziak, P. Gajewski, B. Śnieżyński, V. Deodeshmukh, M. Witkowska, W. Ratuszek, K. Chrusciel, Neural network modelling studies of steam oxidised kinetic behaviour of advanced steels and Ni-based alloys at 800 °C for 3000 h, *Corros. Sci.* 133 (2018) 94–111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2018.01.013>.
- [25] F.H. Stott, G.C. Wood, The mechanism of oxidation of Ni-Cr-Al alloys at 1000°–1200°C, *Corros. Sci.* 11 (1971) 799–812.
- [26] E. Schumann, M. Rühle, Microstructural observations on the oxidation of γ' -Ni₃Al at high oxygen partial pressure, *Acta Metall. Mater.* 42 (1994) 1481–1487.
- [27] P. Huczukowski, N. Christensen, V. Shemet, L. Niewolak, J. Piron-Abellan, L. Singheiser, W.J. Quadackers, Growth mechanisms and electrical conductivity of oxide scales on ferritic steels proposed as interconnect materials for SOFC's, *Fuel Cells Weinh.* (Weinh) 6 (2006) 93–99, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fuce.200500110>.
- [28] B. Hassan, J. Corney, Grain boundary precipitation in Inconel 718 and ATI 718Plus, *Mater. Sci. Technol.* 33 (2017) 1879–1889, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02670836.2017.1333222>.